

Prediction of Creep Rupture Unidirectional Composite (Creep Rupture Model with Interfacial Debonding around Broken Fibers)

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SUMMARY: This paper describes a creep rupture model considering the interfacial debonding in broken fibers in unidirectional polymer matrix composites reinforced by glass fibers. Interfacial debonding is accompanied by fiber breaks under the tensile load, depending on the fiber stress at the moment a fiber breaks and the property of interfacial adhesion. The interfacial debonding length, fiber strength and an interfacial shear stress are investigated by the fragmentation test. Subsequently, the debonding length and a stress recovery length are considered and it is shown that the fiber strength as a function of fiber length is linear and the interfacial debonding length is the longer of the two in the accompaniment of the larger fiber stress. Here the interfacial shear stress is constant. The debonding length is calculated by a energy balance equation used as an interfacial debonding energy Γ_i . The interfacial debonding length is taken in the Curtin's creep rupture model as a function of a stress recovery length. Therefore, this modified Curtin's model can serve for respective properties of the fiber, matrix and interface. Moreover, the unidirectional composites by the use of a vinylester resin matrix reinforced by glass fibers are prepared and the specimen is examined by a creep test. A vinylester/glass fiber interfacial property is investigated according to the fragmentation test. The Curtin's model yields the results to predict the creep rupture time in unidirectional composites. The creep behavior of an unidirectional composite is assumed to depend on viscoelastic characterization of the matrix, and a strain rate of the matrix is determined by the result of the creep test. Furthermore, the result of the creep rupture test displays that creep rupture time on the applied stress is observed experimentally on a unidirectional composite. This result is in good agreement with the creep rupture model considering the interfacial debonding.

KEYWORDS: Interfacial debonding, creep, unidirectional composite and Curtin's model

INTRODUCTION

Assuring long life under tensile stress has been one of the most critical concerns in the application of advanced structural composite materials. To ensure that reliable performance composites do not fail instantaneously and undergo long-term creep. In time, like most materials, fiber composites exhibit one or more transient and steady-state creep stages, and eventually they fail by creep rupture. Common features in most composite creep studies are that time-to-failure is statistical and fiber breaks occur throughout the composite lifetime, being especially intense upon initial loading and time of creep rupture.

McLean [1] has described the creep behavior of a unidirectional composite. It has been assumed that fiber is elastic and matrix is viscoelastic. The increasing total strain of the composite is caused by relaxation of viscoelastic resin tensile stress and by increasing of the elastic fiber stress. Then the matrix viscoelastic behavior is one that the strain rate depends on the matrix tensile stress. In such a way he has described the creep strain behavior as a function of time. Curtin [2] has estimated the rupture strain and maximum fiber's stress of unidirectional composite in order to consider the probability of fiber breaks. Moreover, Du and McMeeking [3~5] have predicted the creep rupture

time of unidirectional composite under the tensile load. They have considered that the strain (stress) of McLean's model had reached to the rupture of that of Curtin's model. But this creep rupture model is over estimated as compared with other experiments. As the contributing factors, there are the stress concentration to the adjacency fibers, the increasing the stress recovery length and the occurrence of the interfacial debonding are prevalent. Clearly, such complexities are undetectable on a macroscopic scale, and thus, we take the micro mechanical behavior, especially the interfacial debonding, into account for the creep rupture model.

Wagner [6~8] has investigated the interfacial debonding length around the fiber breaks of the single fiber within a polymer matrix specimen by a fragmentation test. It has taken the interfacial debonding energy, as an interfacial property, was used in the search for fracture criteria as an energy-based theory. In the present study, the fragmentation test is performed by using a micro composite specimen that comprises a glass single fiber within a dog-bone shape polymer. Also, to investigate the creep parameters the creep test is performed by using unidirectional FRP. Glass fiber/vinylester interfacial properties and the fiber's strength as a function of the fiber's length are estimated by test results. The interfacial shear stress is calculated based on a Kelly-Tyson model by considering the interfacial debonding length at the critical fragment state. The maximum failure strain modified Curtin model considering the interfacial debonding length of unidirectional FRP is estimated from these derived parameters. In this model, it assumes interfacial shear stress on the interfacial debonding area is neglected; in other words, interfacial friction is neglected. It calculates lower failure strain than conventional Curtin model, so it predicts that the creep rupture time will be shorter.

CONVENTIONAL CREEP MODELS

Creep behavior of unidirectional composite

McLean has described the creep strain behavior of a unidirectional composite as follows. He assumes that the fiber is elastic and matrix is viscoelastic, therefore

$$\varepsilon = \sigma_f / E_f \quad (1)$$

$$\dot{\varepsilon} = \dot{\sigma}_m / E_m + B \sigma_m^n \quad (2)$$

where, ε : Total strain

B, n : Creep coefficient

σ_f : Fiber stress

σ_m : Matrix stress

E_f : Young's modulus of fiber

E_m : Young's modulus of matrix

$\dot{(\)}$: Differential for time

Generally, the fiber stress and the matrix stress are concerned as follows in the unidirectional composite.

$$\sigma = (1 - V_f) \sigma_m + V_f \sigma_f$$

V_f : Fiber volume fraction

From these three equations, the total composite strain is indicated as a function of time.

$$\varepsilon(t) = \frac{\sigma}{V_f E_f} - \frac{1 - V_f}{V_f E_f} \left\{ \left(\frac{E_m \sigma}{E_c} \right)^{1-n} + \frac{(n-1) V_f E_f E_m B t}{E_c} \right\}^{1/(1-n)} \quad (3)$$

$$E_c = (1 - V_f) E_m + V_f E_f \quad (4)$$

Where E_c is the total Young's modulus of unidirectional FRP.

Curtin model

Curtin has estimated the fracture strain and stress on

Fig.1 The schematic of fiber stress distribution around the fiber breaking in the random cross-section

the unidirectional FRP in order to consider the probability of fibers in its own cross-section having some thickness. The interfacial shear stress has been assumed constant in the area of stress recovery length(L_f).

The average of fiber stress $\bar{\sigma}_f$ is

$$\bar{\sigma}_f = (1-q)E_f\varepsilon + \frac{qE_f\varepsilon}{2} \quad (5)$$

Here q is the probability of fiber break in the $2L_f$ length. Generally, the fiber break probability is as follows, using Weibull parameters L_0 and σ_0 .

$$P = 1 - \exp\left(-\frac{L}{L_0}\left(\frac{\sigma}{\sigma_0}\right)^m\right) \quad (6)$$

The probability of fiber in this situation, q , is

$$q = 1 - \exp\left(-\frac{2L_f}{L_0}\left(\frac{E_f\varepsilon}{\sigma_0}\right)^m\right) \quad (7)$$

$$\ln(1-q) = -\frac{2L_f}{L_0}\left(\frac{E_f\varepsilon}{\sigma_0}\right)^m \quad (8)$$

When q is small,

$$q = (2L_f/L_0)\left(E_f\varepsilon/\sigma_0\right)^m \quad (9)$$

L_f is as follows, from the force balance equation.

$$L_f = E_f\varepsilon D / 4\tau_0 \quad (10)$$

D : Fiber's diameter

τ_0 : Interfacial shear stress

The fiber probability is described using S_c (characteristic stress)

$$q = \left(\frac{E_f\varepsilon}{S_c}\right)^{m+1} \quad (11)$$

$$S_c = \left(\frac{2\sigma_0^m \tau_0 L_0}{D}\right)^{1/(m+1)} \quad (12)$$

Thus, the average of the fiber stress is

$$\bar{\sigma}_f = E_f\varepsilon \left\{ 1 - \frac{1}{2} \left(\frac{E_f\varepsilon}{S_c}\right)^{m+1} \right\} \quad (13)$$

The maximum value of the fiber stress average is the fracture stress and the strain at that time of the rupture strain of unidirectional FRP and is as follows.

$$S_{\max} = S_c \frac{m+1}{m+2} \left(\frac{2}{m+2}\right)^{1/(m+1)} \quad (14)$$

$$\varepsilon = \frac{S_c}{E_f} \left(\frac{2}{m+2}\right)^{1/(m+1)} \quad (15)$$

Creep rupture model

Du and McMeeking have predicted the creep rupture time of unidirectional composite under the tensile load. They have considered that the strain (stress) of McLean's model had reached to the rupture level of that of Curtin's model, which is as follows

$$t_r = \frac{E_c}{(n-1)V_f E_f E_m B} \left[\left(\frac{1-V_f}{\sigma - V_f S_{\max}}\right)^{n-1} - \left(\frac{E_c}{E_m \sigma}\right)^{n-1} \right] \quad (16)$$

Thus far, it has been possible to predict the creep rupture time coursed from the accumulation of micro damages (fiber breaks) in unidirectional FRP.

SUGGESTION OF NEW CREEP RUPTURE MODEL

The above Curtin's model considers the probability of fiber breaks, however the interfacial debonding is ignored. Interfacial debonding is the fatal damages in which case the interfacial strength is the weakest. We think it needs to take the interfacial debonding into the creep rupture model. We show the fiber stress distribution around the fiber break is in Fig.2. It is assumed that the interfacial shear stress is neglected in the interfacial debonding area.

Fig.2 Fiber tensile stress distribution in the case of interfacial debonding

Fig.3 Stress recovery length change caused by interfacial debonding

For the Curtin model, the interfacial debonding length L_d changes the interfacial debonding length. The probability of fiber breaks and the average of the fiber stress in its own cross-section change accordingly.

$$q = \left(\frac{2L_f + L_d}{L_0} \right) \left(\frac{E_f \varepsilon}{\sigma_0} \right)^m \quad (17)$$

L_d : interfacial debonding length

$$\bar{\sigma}_f = (1-q)E_f \varepsilon + qE_f \varepsilon \frac{L}{2L_f + L_d} \quad (18)$$

Therefore, it is possible to estimate the failure stress and strain considered in the interfacial debonding. The creep rupture time is as follows by the use of the above modified parameters.

$$t_r = \frac{E_c}{(n-1)V_f E_f E_m B} \left[\left(\frac{1-V_f}{\sigma - V_f S'_{max}} \right)^{n-1} - \left(\frac{E_c}{E_m \sigma} \right)^{n-1} \right] \quad (19)$$

S'_{max} : modified maximum fiber stress

EXPERIMENTS

Fragmentation test

We performed the fragmentation test to investigate the interfacial debonding length, the probability of fibers and the interfacial shear stress. Table 1 shows the mechanical properties of the fragmentation specimen and Fig.4 shows the specimen's dimensions. The single fiber is a glass fiber and the matrix is a vinylester.

Young's modulus of fiber	E_f	72GPa
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Fiber diameter	D	22.5 μ m
Gage length	L_0	25mm

The test results were as follows. Firstly, Fig.5 is the fragmentation test result of the interfacial debonding length. Generally speaking, the more the fiber strain increases, the longer interfacial debonding is. In this study, we dealt with the interfacial debonding length along with a quadric as a function of strain. The glass fiber /vinylester interfacial debonding length is

$$L_d = 11 \times \varepsilon^2 + 1.3 \times \varepsilon \quad (20)$$

Secondly, the fiber strength is indicated as follows. The common measurement of the fiber strength by the use of a fragmentation test is a calculation from the relationship of the number of fragments and the fiber's strain. But this method is not available during the condition of a long stress recovery length or an interfacial debonding length. To estimate the relationship of the fiber strength and the fiber length we considered the effective fiber length and we found that it was the length of deducting debonding length and stress recovery length from the one-fragment fiber length as in Fig.6.

The test result of the number of fiber breaks that is considered an effective fiber length as a function of strain is shown in Fig.7.

Fig.6 Tensile stress distribution of fragment fiber

Fig.5 Interfacial debonding length as a function of strain

Fig.7 Number of fiber breaks as a function of strain

From the test results, the relationship the fiber strength and the fiber length is

$$E_f \varepsilon = 2500 \left(\frac{25}{L} \right)^{\frac{1}{13}} \text{ MPa}$$

Thirdly, the interfacial shear stress is calculated from the state of a critical fragment. The critical fragment is a saturation of fiber breaks. At the critical condition, all fiber lengths are less than twice of the stress recovery length, and the interfacial shear stress applies to all areas. If the interfacial shear stress is assumed constant and the interfacial debonding does not exist, it can be estimated as follows [9].

$$\tau = \frac{3E_f \epsilon D}{8 \left(\frac{L_0}{n+1} \right)} \quad (21)$$

Here, n is the number of fiber breaks and L_0 is the gage length. If we considered the interfacial debonding length, the interfacial shear stress is as follows. Here, we assume the interfacial friction stress is neglected

$$\tau = \frac{3E_f \epsilon D}{8 \left(\frac{L_0}{n+1} - L_d \right)} \quad (22)$$

The test results are indicated Table 2. The value of the interfacial debonding length has its own value of the above result its own strain (Fig.5).

Table 2 Critical properties of fragmentation test

Critical strain	ϵ_c	*4.65%
Critical number of fiber breaks	n_c	*33
Interfacial shear stress	τ	51MPa

So far, each static parameter that was needed for the creep rupture model was examined and it was possible to estimate the modified rupture strain of unidirectional glass/vinylester FRP.

Creep test

Creep tests were performed to investigate the creep efficiency. The specimen dimension was like that of the fragmentation test, as well. The fiber bundle transposed from the single fiber was embedded as seen in Fig.8. Fibers and matrix material were same as in the fragmentation test, respectively, and the fiber volume fraction of this specimen was 2%.

Fig.8 Specimen configuration for creep test

Fig.9 displays the creep test result and theoretical curves that bring the test result into correlation with the McLean's model at its own stress level, respectively. From these creep test results, creep constants of Vinylester matrix $B = 2.5 \times 10^{-8} / \text{hour}$, $n = 2.2$, were decided.

**PREDICTION
RUPTURE**

**OF CREEP
AND**

Fig.9 Creep behavior of unidirectional composite

DISCUSSION

The creep lifetime of glass fiber/vinylester unidirectional FRP was predicted with the use of the same static and creep parameters as above. Fig.10 shows the creep time prediction of 2% volume fraction unidirectional FRP specimens. The continuous line in the Fig.10 is the modified creep rupture model and the chain line is the conventional model. The prot is a test result. In this research, the difference between the modified model and the conventional model was very little because the interfacial debonding length was so small that it had no significant impact on the probability of fiber breaks and on the average of the fiber stress in the its own cross-section. However, if the interfacial property is weak and, the interfacial debonding length is long, it effects the fracture strain and stress enormously. Thus, this modified model is clearly more efficient.

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Fig.10 Prediction of creep rupture time

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